

Micro- and nanoplastics as transport vectors for organic contaminants in the environment: A critical review

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The impact of micro- and nanosized plastic particles on the mobility of organic contaminants in the environment is a topic of ongoing scientific debate. Their extensive surface area and capacity to interact with organic contaminants have led to frequent concerns that micro- and nanoplastics significantly enhance their mobility and facilitate contaminant uptake by marine biota. For terrestrial systems, this hypothesis has been adopted, raising concerns that plastic particles could facilitate the transport of contaminants into deeper soil layers, thereby posing a threat to groundwater resources, especially in agricultural soils. These soils receive substantial plastic input through various sources, such as organic soil amendments, mulch, recycled wastewater, and atmospheric deposition. This review examines the molecular interactions between organic contaminants, including a wide range of non-intentionally added substances and additives, and plastic interfaces. We critically analyze the role of micro- and nanoplastics as vectors for contaminants in both marine environments and agricultural soils. Our analysis suggests that the vector effect of contaminants via micro- and nanoplastics in the marine environment is generally insignificant compared to other exposure routes. Our calculations regarding the mass transfer of common plastic additives indicate that the role of micro- and, particularly, nanoplastics as carriers for the majority of organic contaminants in agricultural soils is limited due to rapid desorption rates. Although micro- and nanoplastics do not considerably contribute to transport phenomena as vectors, it is crucial to recognize that they are significant sources of potentially harmful contaminants. These issues must be addressed in the forthcoming INC-5 plastic treaty.

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Introduction

Plastics are pervasive contaminants in the environment. They have been detected in ocean surface waters [1], sediments [2], in rivers and lakes [3,4], on shores [5], in soil [6], ingested by aquatic organisms [7,8], and can be found even in secluded areas such as the Arctic [9] and the mountains [10]. The shapes of plastic debris vary and they range in size from nano- (1–1000 nm) to microplastics (1–1000 µm) [11,12]. Entry pathways of plastics into the aquatic environment include the loss of pellets from pre-production and plastic items during manufacturing and transportation, wear and tear during the life cycle of the plastic product (e.g., fiber losses from textiles, rubber particle abrasion from tire wear, losses during infrastructure construction), improper or inefficient waste management, and littering [13]. Storm-water runoff and direct release are the main sources of land-based plastic litter to the marine environment [1]. Air currents (atmospheric transport) and rivers constitute important transport pathways [14,15]. Under current policies, a total of 44 million tons of plastic are expected to enter the environment annually by 2060 [16].

Agricultural soils are subject to contamination by plastics in a number of ways, most importantly, through

atmospheric deposition and agricultural activities. The latter include the application of organic soil amendments such as compost, biosolids, for example, sludge (which can contain over 300,000 plastic particles per kg [17]), recycled wastewater, and plastic mulch films [14]. Recovery rates of less than 60 % have been reported for mulch films, while substantial quantities remain in the soil where they are subject to degradation processes and fragmentation [18]. In the vicinity of roads, road runoff, splash water, and the resuspension of road dust are critical transport routes for tire wear particles into the soil [19]. In intensively used agricultural soils, up to 43,000 plastic particles were found, with 95 % being microplastics (0.05–1 mm) [20].

Besides the high amount of plastics detected in all environmental compartments, plastics are composed of a plethora of chemical compounds (Figure 1). During the manufacturing of plastic products more than 10,000 chemicals such as monomers, processing aids, and additives (approximately half of the chemicals) are utilized. More than 2400 of these intentionally used plastic chemicals are potentially hazardous given their

persistent, bio-accumulative, toxic, or endocrine disruptive properties [21]. Additives are mixed to the polymer during the manufacturing to ensure processing and achieve the desired properties of the final product [22]. They include UV or heat stabilizers, reinforcements to improve mechanical properties, pigments for coloring, and plasticizers to enhance the flexibility of the plastic product [23]. The amount and type of additives used varies considerably between different polymers. Highest concentrations of additives are found in soft polyvinyl chloride, where plasticizers (especially phthalates) account for up to 70 wt. % of the plastic item [24]. On average, plastic products contain approximately 4 wt.% of additives [25]. With the exception of, for example, a few flame retardants, additives are not chemically bound to the polymer and they can leach into the environment during the life-span of the plastic product [24,26]. In addition to additives, plastics can contain non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) such as side- and breakdown products of polymers and additives as well as contaminants which enter plastics as impurities during manufacturing or are sorbed from the adjacent surroundings [27]. Given the increasing plastic pollution

Figure 1

The complexity of chemicals associated with micro- and nanoplastics (MNP) and possible interactions. Examples of different polymers, additives and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) are shown.

of the environment, high concentrations and a complex mixture of potentially harmful additives can be expected in areas where plastics accumulate.

The simultaneous occurrence of plastics and contaminants in the environment led to the recurring hypothesis that plastic particles could act as transport vectors for these contaminants resulting in an increased uptake by biota. However, regarding the complexity of chemicals associated with plastics, a more differentiated view on the so-called *vector effect*, which takes into account the diversity of chemical properties of contaminants, plastics and possible interactions as well as differences in environmental systems is needed.

In this review, we evaluate the current state of knowledge regarding the interactions between organic contaminants and micro- and nanosized plastic particles, focusing on both the marine environment and agricultural soils. Our analysis encompasses a broad spectrum of NIAS and additives in order to provide a comprehensive overview of chemicals present in plastics. Specifically, we elucidate the role of micro- and nanoplastics for the relocation of organic contaminants and their uptake by biota. Interactions between inorganic contaminants, e.g., metals, and plastic interfaces involve different sorption mechanisms and were therefore not the subject of this study.

Discussion

Interactions of micro- and nanoplastics with organic contaminants

In the environment, hydrophobic organic contaminants (HOCs) can sorb to polar and non-polar interfaces. These include natural particles in soils and sediments, particulate organic matter as well as anthropogenic particles such as micro- and nanoplastics [28]. Over the past decade, numerous studies have shown that micro- and nanoplastics are able to sorb (and desorb) organic contaminants including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) [29], polychlorinated biphenyl (PCBs) [30], pharmaceuticals [31], pesticides [32], and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) [33]. The sorption of contaminants (sorbate phase) to plastics (sorbent phase) involves surface *adsorption* and *absorption* into the polymer matrix [34]. While adsorption of non-polar organic contaminants mainly involves non-specific van der Waals forces, absorption also involves hydrogen bonding, steric and π electron-donor acceptor interactions [28,35]. For polymers with conjugated C=C bonds such as polystyrene (PS) and styrene-butadiene rubber (a main component of tire materials) and, for example, contaminants with chemical structures containing aromatic hydrocarbon rings, π - π interactions can occur [35]. Permanently charged and ionizable organic compounds (IOCs), including zwitterions with both positively and negatively charged moieties, interact

with the sorbate through electrostatic interactions with sorption being strongly dependent on the pH of the system [36]. Among the REACH registered organic chemicals with an identified chemical structure, more than half (56 %) are neutral at environmentally relevant pH values (pH = 4–9), while the remaining ones are charged, ionizable or zwitterionic [37]. The influence of the respective molecular interactions on the overall sorption process depends on the properties of the contaminant and polymer under consideration as well as on the environmental conditions [35].

The equilibrium distribution coefficient ($K_d = c_s c_w^{-1}$, $L kg^{-1}$), which is defined as the ratio of the contaminant concentration in the solid phase (c_s , $kg kg^{-1}$) to that in the water phase (c_w , $kg L^{-1}$), is a commonly used parameter to quantify sorption affinity [36]. The distribution coefficient between the polymer and water, $K_{POLYMER/W}$ often correlates with hydrophobicity for neutral, non-polar contaminants and can be predicted based on, for example, its relationship with the subcooled liquid aqueous solubility ($mol m^{-3}$), the solubility ($kg L^{-1}$), the molecular weight or the octanol-water partition coefficients ($K_{O/W}$) of the contaminant. These correlations are most suitable when contaminant absorption into the polymer is the main sorption mechanism (e.g., for polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP)) [34]. For PE mainly van der Waals interactions are involved and calculations using the saturated aqueous concentration or the contaminants' solubility were most suitable to predict $K_{PE/W}^{38}$. Nevertheless, these concepts are inadequate for predicting the sorption of IOCs and may result in erroneous estimations of partition coefficients [37,38]. To accurately predict the partition coefficient, it is essential to consider the complexity of possible sorption interactions and the influence of environmental conditions, such as pH and the ionic composition of water [36,37].

Micro- and nanoplastics are not a major vector for organic contaminants in marine environments

Non-intentionally added substances

The ability of micro- and nanoplastics to sorb and transport hydrophobic organic contaminants has led to the repeatedly raised concerns in the scientific community and the society that microplastics could act as a transport vector for these contaminants in the marine environment, thereby facilitating the uptake of contaminants by biota. To investigate the vector effect, it is not only important to study the interactions between plastic particles and organic contaminants, but also to analyze the role of micro- and nanoplastics to carry organic contaminants against the background of other exposure pathways for marine organisms.

For micro- and nanoplastics-facilitated transport to be relevant, the abundance of micro- and nanoplastics and

their affinity to sorb contaminants need to be high [39]. While micro- and nanoplastics are ubiquitous in the marine environment, their volume and thus capacity to sorb contaminants is relatively small, limiting the uptake of contaminants bound to plastic particles by biota compared to other uptake routes like water, natural prey, and particles, as well as dermal exposure and uptake through the skin [39–41]. For a representative coastal model environment consisting of air, water and sediment, sorption of organic contaminants to polyethylene was calculated to be less than 0.1 % [40]. Likewise, the amount of microplastic-bound hydrophobic contaminants in the ocean was found to be negligible ($<2 \times 10^{-4}$ %) in comparison to other environmental media when partitioning was included for dissolved organic carbon, carbon black, and biota at low trophic levels (for example, phytoplankton or zooplankton). It should be noted that a high sorption affinity of organic contaminants to plastics was assumed ($K_{\text{POLYMER}/\text{W}} = 7$). Even when only particulate phases were considered, the fraction of contaminants bound to microplastics was limited (2×10^{-2} %) [39].

The uptake and release of organic contaminants is determined by the fugacity gradient of contaminants between micro- and nanoplastics and adjacent phases. It depends on the residence time of the micro- and nanoplastics. Only if the fugacity in the micro- and nanoplastics is higher than in the surrounding media, contaminants are released until equilibrium is reached [26]. The influence of dynamic environmental factors can result in local disruptions of equilibrium conditions at the plastic interface. Comparing the residence times of plastics in the marine environment (3 years for 90 % and 19 years for 50 % of plastics in 2022, Fig. S1) to leaching half-lives of contaminants (weeks to less than 2 years for hydrophobic contaminants, e.g., PAHs) [39], most micro- and nanoplastics in the ocean have reached sorption equilibrium for organic contaminants. Therefore, the release of contaminants from micro- and nanoplastics into the ocean is limited to a few cases of very hydrophobic contaminants with long equilibration times or freshly introduced micro- and nanoplastics which have not yet reached sorption equilibrium. While the global plastic production increased rapidly during the past decade (e.g., from 288 Mt in 2012 to 400 Mt in 2022) [42,43], the fraction of newly introduced plastics compared to the cumulative plastic inventory in the ocean remained constant at approximately ~ 3 %. The calculations assumed a constant fraction of the globally produced plastics to be released into the marine environment [44]. In view of the pace at which the global plastic production is increasing, the fraction of fresh plastics might increase in the future. It can be assumed that calculations based on leaching from pristine micro- and nanoplastics overestimate leaching half-lives under environmental conditions, given the influence of environmental factors on contaminant release [45]. If both

the micro- and nanoplastics and the aquatic organisms present in the same marine environment are in equilibrium with the surrounding contaminants, the uptake of micro- and nanoplastics by aquatic organisms does not change the organisms' level of contamination. Scenarios in which either micro- and nanoplastics or organisms are *clean* with respect to the contaminant under consideration are rather unlikely in the environment [46].

Although there is little evidence that micro- and nanoplastics play a relevant role in the translocation of organic pollutants in the marine environment, the vector effect of micro- and nanoplastics is still described in the literature as complex and inconclusive [47]. This is mainly because 'relevant' studies address different research questions. To harmonize the research results and improve clarity on the role of micro- and nanoplastics in facilitating contaminant transport, quality criteria for laboratory, field, and model studies have been outlined in the literature. These can be used to investigate the vector effect of micro- and nanoplastics under environmentally relevant conditions in the context of chemical risk assessment. For laboratory studies, a suitable experimental design should include the consideration of i) multiple uptake pathways of contaminants (i.e., all that are present in the environment under investigation), ii) sufficiently long equilibration times for loading micro- and nanoplastics with target contaminants, iii) pre-equilibrated micro- and nanoplastics, exposure media and test organisms with contaminants (since this is the most likely scenario in the environmental), iv) the ability of test organisms to ingest micro- and nanoplastic particles used in the study, v) bidirectional chemical transfer from micro- and nanoplastics to biota and reverse and vi) exceedance of chemical threshold values (e.g., the predicted no effect concentration (PNEC)) taking into account effects of chemical mixtures [48].

Additives

When concerns were raised about the vector effect of micro- and nanoplastics, additives were often considered to be particularly important. This is because additives, such as plasticizers and flame retardants, can account for up to 70 wt.% of plastic items leading to a (probably) higher fugacity of additives in the plastic phase than in the environment, which promotes their release [24,26]. As discussed earlier for NIAS, micro- and nanoplastics in the marine environment result from slow fragmentation processes (slower than desorption times) and have long residence times (>3 years). Similar to NIAS, the most probable scenario for the release of additives from micro- and nanoplastics is that a state of equilibrium has been reached [48]. Given that there is a negligible fugacity gradient under environmentally relevant conditions, the low abundance of micro- and nanoplastics compared to other uptake pathways also limits the vector effect for additives. Modeling studies showed that microplastic-facilitated uptake of additives such as bi-2-ethylhexyl

phthalate (DEHP) or bisphenol A by biota was negligible compared to the uptake through, for example, water and food [41,49].

Our conclusion that the role of micro- and nanoplastics as transport vectors for organic contaminants in marine environments is limited should not be interpreted as diminishing the harmful effects of chemical pollution associated with plastic particles. Specifically, for harmful additives, such as phthalates and bisphenols, which are known to interfere with the endocrine system, plastics represent a significant source for the release of these contaminants into the environment, with potentially detrimental health consequences for aquatic organisms. Plastic regulations must therefore carefully consider the flux of additives to aquatic environments.

Micro- and nanoplastics are not a major vector for most organic contaminants in agricultural soils

Non-intentionally added substances

Concerns about the role of micro- and nanoplastics as a vector for organic contaminants and enhanced uptake by biota were also raised with regard to agricultural soil systems [50,51]. The hypothesis was adopted and concerns were raised that plastic particles could facilitate the vertical transport of contaminants such as pesticides into deeper soil layers, possibly threatening groundwater resources [52]. To address these concerns, the principal criteria for assessing the vector effect outlined for marine environments can be transferred to soil systems. In order for micro- and nanoplastics-facilitated vertical transport of organic contaminants to be environmentally relevant, the abundance of micro- and nanoplastics in soil must be high, the contaminant must be a cause of concern, the mobility of micro- and nanoplastics-bound contaminants must be higher than the mobility of non-sorbed contaminants and, desorption of the contaminants from the micro- and nanoplastic particles during the transport time must be slow [53,54].

Castan *et al.* (2021) studied the potential role of micro- and nano-sized polymers such as polyethylene and tire material as carriers for a range of organic contaminants, including PAHs, PCBs, pesticides, and pharmaceuticals in agricultural soil systems. The diffusion times of contaminants from plastic particles (100 nm- 1 mm) were assessed using two diffusion models, that is, intraparticle diffusion (IPD) and aqueous boundary layer diffusion (ABLD), and related to the travel times of micro- and nanoplastics using the so-called Damköhler number (Da) [55]. The Damköhler number is a well-known concept to assess the relative importance of advective versus diffusive transport processes. $Da > 100$ (equilibrium transport) indicate that contaminants are released rapidly during vertical plastic particle transport and equilibrium is established. $Da < 0.01$ (decoupled transport) indicate that contaminants

are released slowly and can be transported with the micro- and nanoplastics. For Da between 0.01 and 100, kinetic transport conditions prevail [56]. For the majority of particle sizes, contaminants and polymers, the desorption kinetics were too fast (equilibrium transport prevailed) for micro- and nanoplastics-facilitated transport in the soil to be relevant. Decoupled transport was only relevant in case of highly hydrophobic contaminants combined with particles in fast preferential flow conditions [55]. The desorption rates were based on calculations for rather pristine particles and the influence of the environmental factors was not considered. Photoaging, for instance, can result in an increase in the surface hydrophilicity of the plastics which, in turn, leads to reduced K_{PE} [57]. The presence of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) can facilitate the transport of contaminants through the aqueous boundary layer which also results in reduced K_{PE} [58,59]. Mechanical stress can lead to fragmentation, which reduces the particle size and thereby the diffusion distance [60]. Furthermore, a high particle mobility was assumed, which excluded interactions of micro- and nanoplastics with the soil. When the effect of environmental factors and interactions are taken into account, the transport of contaminants bound to micro- and nanoplastics into deeper soil layer becomes less likely. The release of plastic-associated chemicals into upper soil layers, where they can be taken up by (edible) plants and soil organisms, poses a threat to soil ecosystems. In particular, the release of harmful contaminants stresses the importance of protecting soils from plastic pollution.

Additives

Castan *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that micro- and nanoplastics do not significantly enhance the mobility of organic contaminants in soil [55]. However, less than 30 additives were considered, including mainly UV-stabilizers, amine stabilizers used in the production of tire rubber and plasticizers (mainly phthalates), which might not reflect the chemical diversity of plastic additives. In the following section, we expand the number to >150 of common plastic additives encompassing a wide range of chemical compound classes and we update the assessment of the relevance of micro- and nanoplastics for vertical contaminant relocation in soil.

The European Chemicals Agency's (ECHA) list of plastic additives registered under REACH with a high production volume (>100 tons per year) was used to extract a representative set of organic additives which may be present in agricultural soils [61]. The initial list comprised 418 additives, accompanied by the respective CAS number, the additive's function in plastics, polymers the additive is used for, and typical concentration in plastics. For this analysis, inorganics, organometallics which contain at least one metal bond, e.g., with copper, strontium or tin, and single element compounds such as

carbon black were excluded (Figure 2). Multi-constituent substances including reaction masses where the parent compounds but not the reaction product was given and compounds for which complete chemical information was not available were also excluded. Chemical information of the remaining compounds (chemical formula, SMILES, molecular weight, molecular volume, solubility, K_{OW} and pKa values) were compiled using the cheminformatics tool *Chemicalize* of the software *Chemaxon* [62]. *Chemicalize* uses structure-based information for the prediction of physical-chemical properties of a molecule. Uncertainties using cheminformatics tools may arise, for example, from the underlying training dataset of the model. Based on the pKa values, compounds that are zwitterionic, charged, or ionizable at environmentally relevant pH (pH = 4–9) were not considered. The outlined procedure yielded a list of 153 organic, neutral plastic additives with complete chemical information (Table S1). These additives were divided into the following functional groups: Plasticizers, flame retardants, pigments, antioxidants, heat and light stabilizers, other stabilizers, antistatic agents and additives with other functions.

To evaluate the importance of micro- and nanoplastics for the relocation of plastic additives in soil more systematically, we employed the analytical approach described by Castan et al. (2021) using the more representative set of plastic additives (Figure 2) [55]. The details of the calculations are provided in the Supporting Information. Transport processes were differentiated according to the Damköhler number as follows:

fully decoupled: $Da \leq 0.01$

mainly decoupled: $0.01 \leq Da \leq 0.1$

mainly equilibrium: $10 \leq Da \leq 100$

fully equilibrium: $Da \geq 100$

Damköhler numbers were calculated using a broad range of theoretical partition and diffusion coefficients for plastic particles with a size of 0.1–1000 μm . Castan et al. (2021) compared the partition and diffusion coefficients to values reported in the literature to determine whether decoupled transport of contaminants is possible [55]. In this study, we used polyethylene as a model polymer to analyze plastic-bound additive transport. Polyethylene is the most widely produced polymer accounting for more than 105 Mt (26.3 %) of the global plastics production in 2022 [43]. The type of additive used varies among plastics items and the quantities added may vary for different polymers. Thus, calculations can be adapted accordingly, if specific plastic items are considered.

The partition coefficient between polyethylene and water, $K_{PE/W}$ (L kg^{-1}), was calculated for each additive using the linear free-energy relationship with the intrinsic solubility of the compound (Equation S5). The diffusion coefficient in polyethylene D_{PE} ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) was calculated based on the relationship with the molar volume of the additive (Equation S3) [38]. While Castan et al. (2021) used a constant ABL thickness of 300 μm to account for slow flow conditions (1 m year^{-1}) in soil [55], we used an ABL thickness of 300 μm for microplastics with a radius of 1 mm and scaled the ABL thickness for smaller sized particles using the relationship with the Sherwood number (Equation S7) [60]. While the investigation of additives considered here is not exhaustive, it covers a more representative spectrum of compound classes, and given the observed range of $\log K_{PE}$ (0–18) and $\log D_{PE}$ (–11 to –28), includes compounds with very different sorption properties (Table S1).

For intraparticle diffusion-limited mass transfer processes, nanoplastics did not play a role in facilitating the transport of additives (Figure 3) because the desorption of additives was too rapid. For fully decoupled transport of additives by nanoplastics, $\log D_{PE}$ of additives lower than –25 were required. This was only the case for three

Figure 2

Overview of the procedure to assess a representative set of organic, neutral plastic additives. Obtained compounds for each analysis step are highlighted in green, those that were excluded from further analysis are highlighted in yellow. The number of additives considered for each step are provided.

Figure 3

Identification of micro- and nanoplastics facilitated transport of additives assuming intraparticle diffusion-limited mass transfer of additives and slow flow conditions (1 m a^{-1}) in agricultural soils. Damköhler numbers for fully and mainly decoupled transport, $Da = 0.01$ and $Da = 0.1$, respectively, and for fully and mainly equilibrium transport, $Da = 100$ and $Da = 10$, respectively, are indicated by solid and dashed lines. Damköhler numbers were calculated for micro- and nanoplastics with a diameter of 100 nm to 1 mm (x-axis) using a range of theoretical logarithmic diffusion coefficients in polyethylene $\log D_{PE}$ (y-axis) (left panel). For comparison, calculated $\log D_{PE}$ for different groups of additives are shown (right panel). The figure was adapted from Castan *et al.* (2021) using an extended set of plastic additives [55].

additives: pentaerythritol tetrakis(3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl) propionate) ($C_{73}H_{108}O_{12}$), an antioxidant, hydrogenated castor oil ($C_{57}H_{110}O_9$), a lubricant, and sorbitan tristearate ($C_{60}H_{114}O_8$), an emulsifier. The first two compounds are on the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's *safer chemical ingredients list* and are expected to be of low concern [63]. Sorbitan tristearate is a common food additive (E 492) [64]. For medium-sized (100 μm) and large microplastics (1 mm), fully decoupled transport was observed for a limited number of cases involving primarily pigment agents and antioxidants with $\log D_{PE}$ values lower than -21 and -19 , respectively. These additives have a relatively high molar volume of $\geq 752 \text{ \AA}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for $\log D_{PE} = -21$) and $\geq 614 \text{ \AA}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for $\log D_{PE} = -19$) and diffuse more slowly through the polymer. The majority of additives considered in this study did not meet these criteria: approximately 92 % of the additives had $\log D_{PE}$ greater than -21 and approximately 84 % had $\log D_{PE}$ greater than -19 , indicating that microplastics-facilitated vertical transport of additives is of limited relevance.

D_{PE} decreases with decreasing additive concentration in the polymer due to the lower free volume and mobility of the polymer molecules [65]. Concentration-

dependent changes of the diffusion coefficient become more relevant for polymers with a higher additive content than polyethylene, such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC) [66]. For instance, in highly plasticized PVC, D_{PVC} can decrease over several orders of magnitude with proceeding desorption slowing down IPD and leading to a shift of the governing mass transfer process from ABLD to IPD [45]. Throughout our calculations, constant desorption rates were assumed.

For aqueous boundary layer diffusion-limited mass transfer, fully decoupled transport of additives by nanoplastics was limited to ten additives with $\log K_{PE} \geq 14$, which equaled less than 7 % of the additives considered in this study (Figure 4). These highly hydrophobic additives included pigment agents (pigment red 178, $C_{48}H_{26}N_6O_4$), antioxidants (distearyl thiodipropionate, $C_{42}H_{82}O_4S$; 1-(octadecylsulfanyl)octadecane, $C_{36}H_{74}S_2$; distearyl pentaerythritol diphosphite, $C_{41}H_{82}O_6P_2$), stabilizers (tris(11-methyldodecyl) phosphite, $C_{39}H_{81}O_3P$; ethylene bis(stearamide), $C_{38}H_{76}N_2O_2$) and additives with other functions (glyceryl tristearate, $C_{57}H_{110}O_6$; hydrogenated castor oil, $C_{57}H_{110}O_9$; stearyl erucamide, $C_{40}H_{79}NO$; sorbitan tristearate, $C_{60}H_{114}O_8$). For most nanoplastics, desorption rates were high and nanoplastics-facilitated

Figure 4

Identification of micro- and nanoplastics facilitated transport of additives assuming aqueous boundary layer diffusion-limited mass transfer of additives and slow flow conditions (1 m a^{-1}) in agricultural soils. Damköhler numbers for fully and mainly decoupled transport, $Da = 0.01$ and $Da = 0.1$, respectively, and for fully and mainly equilibrium transport, $Da = 100$ and $Da = 10$, respectively, are indicated by solid and dashed lines. Damköhler numbers were calculated for micro- and nanoplastics with a diameter of 100 nm to 1 mm (x-axis) using a range of theoretical logarithmic partition coefficients for polyethylene $\log K_{PE}$ (y-axis) (left panel). For comparison, calculated $\log K_{PE}$ for different groups of additives are shown (right panel). The figure was adapted from Castan et al. (2021) using an extended set of plastic additives [55].

additive transport was irrelevant. For smaller-sized (10 μm), medium-sized (100 μm) and larger microplastics (1 mm), fully decoupled transport, i.e., where microplastics served as vectors for organic contaminants, was only possible for additives with $\log K_{PE} \geq 12$, $\log K_{PE} \geq 10$, and $\log K_{PE} \geq 8$, respectively. $\log K_{PE} \geq 8$ have been identified for compounds from various additive groups including plasticizers, flame retardants, antioxidants and pigments. For larger microplastics (1 mm) and the majority of additives (61 %), decoupled transport did not occur. With decreasing particle size, desorption rates increase and decoupled transport becomes less likely. For medium-sized (100 μm) and smaller-sized microplastics (10 μm), decoupled transport was not possible for 79 % and 88 % of additives, respectively. As previously discussed in the context of non-intentionally added substances, the assumption of high particle mobility and the exclusion of environment factors may lead to an overestimation of the potential of additive relocation by micro- and nanoplastics under environmental conditions. Regarding the uptake process by biota, it can be assumed that *ultra-hydrophobic* additives with a $\log K_{PE} > 8$ have a low potential for bioaccumulation due to their low water solubility and large molecular size [26].

Conclusion

In the environment, plastics can interact with organic contaminants in various ways, with sorption processes playing a crucial role. This has led to numerous studies raising concerns about the *vector effect* and investigating sorption of organic contaminants to plastics. The ability to sorb and transport organic contaminants, however, is not sufficient to prove such vector effect. This review has shown that there is *lack of evidence* for most organic substances to support the hypothesis of the vector effect of non-intentionally added substances and additives through micro- and nanoplastics in the marine environments and in agricultural soils. Rapid release rates and the establishment of equilibrium conditions limit the translocation of contaminants. Although nanoplastics are highly mobile in the environment and therefore often suspected to be relevant for the transport of contaminants, our results demonstrate that in most cases they do not play a significant role in the relocation of either NIAS or additives. Only for large particle sizes (mainly $\geq 1 \text{ mm}$), very hydrophobic substances, and a time frame of 1 year (and shorter), microplastics might contribute to the contaminant relocation in soil. In marine as well as soil systems, micro- and nanoplastics reach equilibrium for longer time frames.

However, chemical additives in plastic are significant sources of environmental contaminants, causing detrimental effect on the health of aquatic and terrestrial organisms, as well as humans. They substantially contribute to the global flux of undesired substances into the environment and must be strictly regulated in the forthcoming INC-5 plastic treaty.

Credit author statement

Charlotte Henkel: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing.

Thorsten Hüffer: Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition.

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Thilo Hofmann: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cocis.2025.101934>.

Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article (and its Supporting Information files and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15512711>).

References

Papers of particular interest, published within the period of review, have been highlighted as:

- * of special interest
- ** of outstanding interest

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